

EFFECTS OF MOBILE LEGENDS GAMING ON THE ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE OF GRADE 6 LEARNERS

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Abstract. This study aimed to determine the effects of Mobile Legends gaming on the academic performance of Grade 6 Learners at Mandaluyong Addition Hills Elementary School, Mandaluyong City during the School Year 2021-2022. This study made use of a descriptive-correlational research design. The subjects of the study were the Grade 6 learners who indulged in playing Mobile Legends. A 15-item questionnaire was administered to the learners by the respective class advisers in each section via Google Forms. Parents and guardians were requested to help and assist the learners in answering all the items in the questionnaire. The results further revealed that there is no significant relationship between learners' profiles: sex, frequency of playing, average time spent, and online attitudes and their academic performance. The study recommends that home learning partners or parents should continue to guide learners to limit their game exposure and help them excel in their studies. Learners should be encouraged to improve further their academic performance to outstanding and excellent. Moreover, it widens the scope of the study and identifies more factors that can affect the learners' academic performance. Similar studies should be conducted to determine the mobile gaming habits of learners and how they affect their performance in school.

Keywords. Gaming, Academic Performance, Online Gaming Attitudes, Average Time Spent

1 Introduction

When the whole world was faced with the threat of the current pandemic due to COVID-19, every country was forced to be locked down, including the Philippines. Schools are closed, recreational spaces, malls, and even stores. Since the nationwide quarantine in the Philippines started, the Department of Education (DepEd) decided to shift from face-to-face learning to online learning, as per President Rodrigo Duterte's directive to delay physical school activities while the country is suffering from the outbreak.

The implementation of the suspension of all face-to-face school operations was one of the efforts to stop the spread of the virus and to ensure the safety of all learners and school personnel. Also, ages below 21 are not allowed to go outside, as a part of strict quarantine protocols. This range of ages falls under the category of Generation Z. Gen Z learners are known to be the most adaptable and knowledgeable when it comes to modern technology.

According to Kishimoto (2021), being in lockdown means Filipino Gen Z learners will likely find more time to relax at home—with mobile games keeping them entertained. Aviso et al. (2021) stated that, since many learners are staying at home due to the pandemic, online games have grown increasingly popular. They spend a lot of time playing online games.

We are living in a very advanced digital world, and it includes online games that engage a massive number of users. However, academic performance is an essential factor in the lives of young individuals and the nation, as it determines how well both will do.

Moreover, learners nowadays spend too much time playing online games, especially during this time of pandemic when everyone is stuck at home. Online games became one of the daily habits of a learner during these times. Many people like online gaming as a hobby. For some, playing video games is a stress relief, a challenge and competition, relaxation, enjoyment, social connection, and even a mental escape from the actual world (Dumrique, et al., 2018). Teenagers' use of social media and the internet was high even before the government implemented a COVID-19 lockdown (Kirkaburun & Griffiths, 2018). In addition to this, online gaming is one of the most popular pastimes for teenagers, kids, and learners. Teens who play online games are having fun, say Kuss & Griffiths (2018). They play not only out of seriousness but also to

feel relieved. During school hours, learners tend to feel anxious owing to heavy workloads, and playing will help them relax.

Playing video games is one of the ways a learner can be entertained at present. Back then, learners would go around outdoors and play different kinds of street sports or games. In the Philippines, the highlight of everyone's childhood are the famous street games like: patintero, langit-lupa-impverno, teks, turumpo, sipa, chinese garter, tagu-taguan, luksong baka, luksong tinik, tumbang preso, etc. However, with the progress of generations, and the rise and development of modern technology, digital gadgets were created, and different online games are what keep learners today entertained, rather than going out in the sweltering heat and playing street games. One of the factors that forbid the learners from going out is the COVID-19 pandemic where everything is forced to be closed restraining them from going outside. That is why learners today mostly rely on online games for their fun time. One of these games that are popular with kids today is Mobile Legends.

Mobile Legends is a free-to-play game available on Android and iOS that is monetized through purchasing in-game characters and skins. This game pits two teams of five players against each other, intending to destroy the opposing team's base. Each player chooses a hero at the start of the game. Each hero has his or her own set of characteristics and abilities. In the game, there are 92 heroes divided into six categories: tank, fighter, assassin, marksman, support, and wizard. Players' obligations for their respective teams are determined by these positions. Support heroes, for example, can enhance or heal their comrades. That is why, to keep their comrades alive or powerful in war, they need to remain with them. Players must also destroy opposing forces, notably computer-controlled minions and turrets, to level up their heroes. This earns them coins which players can use to purchase equipment that improves their heroes' attributes. The run time of playing Mobile Legends often takes 10 to 15 minutes depending on the players.

An online game is a video game that is played in part or entirely over the Internet or any other accessible computer network. Many online games form their online communities, while others, particularly social games, include the players' existing offline communities. Because many well-known Twitch streamers and YouTubers play certain online games, they can gain a lot of attention. Spending too much time playing online games affects not only health, behavior, and concentration, but also learning ability and academic performance. Some experts claim the positive effects of online gaming (Anderson, C. A. et. Al 2018).

As online games especially Mobile Legends continue to grow, the researcher is not new to such scenarios where learners like to play their games. Online games that are the product of dynamic modern technologies become too enticing an entertainment type to be ignored.

A Grade 6 learner of Mandaluyong Addition Hills Elementary School piqued the researcher's interest. The researcher noticed the learner playing Mobile Legends rather than doing his homework daily. Whenever the deadline for submission arrives, the learner is always overburdened with activities, causing the learner to cram and finish his tasks in a rush to meet the deadlines. In a classroom scenario, during lunchtime or breaktime, learners will gather around in circles and play on their phones. In such instances, some learners try to play games secretly while teachers are teaching. Due to playing online games, a quarrel between learners as one is non-participative in activities, or one is too demanding has already reached the researcher's attention. There are also instances that learners get physical and do such violent acts. On the other hand, the researcher also noticed players with good leadership skills as they plan and command their groupmates. Critical and tactical skills are already shown by such learners which resulted in such outstanding performance. This only shows that online gaming creates both positive and negative results. This prompted the researcher to conduct this study to determine whether playing online games affects learners' academic performance.

2 Review of Related Literature

Based on the foregoing information, previous research, and investigations, the researcher designed this study to discover other elements that may influence or impact the learners' academic performance but focuses on the main topic: playing Mobile Legends. The related literature and studies included here were chosen for their relevance to this topic. Different literature and studies were assessed and presented thoroughly.

In general, video games potentially harm not only physical but also mental health. Labana et al. (2020) emphasized the negative effects of video game addiction. Some effects include stress, loss of control, anger, and such. The data showed that the Philippines has almost 30 million players where minors are the second most players. Moodiness and other emotional health issues can be seen in these age groups.

Meanwhile, M. Griffiths & Ph.D. (2009), and Eugenio showed the beneficial effect of online gaming. Comprehension, math, teamwork, typing, and the like can be gained by playing video games. It debunks the popular negative belief about video games as they improve brain and muscle performance. These studies give the researcher an expectation of the attitudes of the learners. The mentioned studies are broad and did not choose a specific game to study. As the current study focuses on Mobile Legends, it can give a closer look at its effects on its users.

De Los Santos et al., (2020) focused on the academic performance of university students. Meanwhile, Dumrique and Castillo (2018) studied the effects of online gaming on high school learners. Both studies aimed to determine the effects of online gaming on the academic performance of learners. The studies of Verecio (2017) and Garnada (2020) also discussed the effects of online gaming on tertiary students. However, the studies mentioned do not specify the type of game played making it broad. Meanwhile, the present study targets Grade 6 learners who are playing Mobile Legends specifically.

Generally, the preceding studies were relevant to the study. They have a common theme, which is online gaming, although different results were obtained. The researcher believed that these studies could greatly aid in the completion of the present study.

3 Research Methodology

3.1 Research Design

The descriptive correlational research design was used in this study. It attempts to determine the extent of a relationship between two or more variables using statistical data. In this type of design, relationships between and among several facts are sought and interpreted. The data, relationships, and distributions of variables are studied only. Variables are not manipulated; they are only identified and studied as they occur in a natural setting. The study of de Los Santos et al used university students and a variety of online games. The only difference between the study of de Los Santos et al to the current study is that the current study used elementary learners and a specific game. This narrowed down the scope and made it more specific.

3.2 Sources of Data

The subjects of the study are the Grade 6 learners, specifically the gamers at Mandaluyong Addition Hills Elementary School during the school year 2021-2022. Since there are five (5) sections in Grade 6 and not all learners are playing Mobile Legends, the researcher made use of a purposive sampling method to determine the number of respondents to participated in the study.

3.3 Statistical Treatment of Data

To attain valid and reliable results from the data gathered, appropriate statistical tools were used. For the learner's sex, the researcher used the frequency count and percentage to clearly show the fraction of Grade 6 gamers by sex. For the learner's frequency of playing Mobile Legends, a 5-point Likert scale was used. The scale contains five choices, each with a given numerical value. Average weighted mean was determined and interpreted For the average time spent in playing mobile legends, the researcher made use of the scheme shown below. The average weighted mean of the learners' responses was computed and given descriptive equivalent

For the online gaming attitudes, the researcher used a 5-point Likert scale. The scale contains five choices having numerical equivalents. The average weighted mean of their responses to each attitude statement was computed. The researcher obtained the data from the records of the Grade 6 learners' advisers for their average during the first and second quarters of, the school year 2021-2022. The general average was computed, and the results were interpreted. Test

of significance of the relationships or association between the variables under study was employed using the Chi-square test. Data that were gathered in this regard were processed through the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS).

4 Presentation, Analysis, and Interpretation of Data

This study intended to present the profile of the Grade 6 learners at Mandaluyong Addition Hills Elementary School during the school year 2021-2022. Table 2A shows the profile of the Grade 6 Learners in terms of sex, frequency of playing, and average time spent playing mobile legends. The table shows that 23 or 63.89% of the total respondents are males and 13 or 33.11% are females. It clearly shows that more males are playing online games. The results on the variable frequency of playing revealed that the Grade 6 learners seldom play Mobile Legends with an average weighted mean of 2.28, meaning they only play twice a week. It can be inferred that the learners have more time to study their self-learning modules and work on their performance tasks.

On the average time spent playing, the table reflects that Grade 6 learners spend 1 to 2 hours a day, which corresponds to a short time. This implies that the learners observe discipline while playing Mobile Legends which could be imposed by their parents or guardians. This allows the learners to complete more and be productive because their attention is focused and they have good time management skills. Furthermore, learners can perform their tasks on time and have more time for activities that are important to them, such as sports, hobbies, youth group, and spending time with friends and family, if they use time efficiently.

Table 2A. Profile of the Grade 6 Learners in Terms of Sex, Frequency of Playing and Average Time Spent Playing Mobile Legends
N=36

Variables	Frequency (<i>f</i>)		Percentage
Sex			
Male	23		63.89%
Female	13		36.11%
Total	36		100%
Frequency of Playing	(<i>f</i>)	Average Weighted Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Everyday	6	2.28	Seldom
5 to 6 times a week	1		
3 to 4 times a week	7		
Twice a week	5		
Once a week	17		
Total	36		
Average Time Spent in Playing	(<i>f</i>)	Average Weighted Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
More than 6 hours	1	1.72	Short time
5-6 hours in a day	1		
3-4 hours in a day	3		
1-2 hours in a day	13		
Less than 1 hour in a day	18		
Total	36		

Table 2B shows the result of the online gaming attitudes of learners. Statements on the table reflect different attitudes and behaviors of learners such as; choosing priorities, forgetfulness, teamwork, and manners. Statements 2 and 3 show a positive result based on the average weighted mean of 3.77 and 3.61 respectively. It means that learners prioritize the tasks that must be completed before playing the game. Prioritization is essential because it helps learners to focus their attention on school-related activities that are more important. Although statement 4 reflects a negative result, this tells that the learners can think independently. As a result, they understand the difference between situations that they can manage on their own and those that require outside assistance.

Statements 1, 5, and 6 resulted in neutral. It is comprehensible since the feelings of gamers depend on the flow of the game. It can be inferred that gamers find the game easy because they are matched with weak opponents or find it hard because they are matched with advanced opponents. The learners can sometimes be happy because they win the battles or can sometimes be angry because they lose. Meanwhile, statements 7, 8, and 9 have positive results and statement 10 has a neutral outcome. These statements reflect the manners and teamwork of the learners while playing the game. Mobile Legends involve cooperating with your teammates and talking with them through chat or voice, which can improve their ability to work with other people and have better social interactions even when playing games.

Table 2B. Online Gaming Attitudes of the Grade 6 Learners
 N=36

Attitude Statements	Average Weighted Mean	Descriptive Equivalent	Category
1. I find it easy to play Mobile Legends	3.47	Neutral	Neutral
2. I always choose schoolwork over playing Mobile Legends	3.77	Agree	Positive
3. I never forget doing my assignments and activities.	3.61	Agree	Positive
4. I always acknowledge suggestions from my teammates when playing Mobile Legends.	2.25	Disagree	Negative
5. Mobile Legends does not make me angry.	3.16	Neutral	Neutral
6. Mobile Legends makes me happy.	2.83	Neutral	Neutral
7. Mobile Legends does not make me sad.	4.30	Agree	Positive
8. I do not utter curse words when playing Mobile Legends.	4.22	Agree	Positive
9. I act nicely when playing Mobile Legends	3.66	Agree	Positive
10. I show gestures of courtesy to my teammates and opponents when playing the game like saying "sorry" and "thank you".	2.97	Neutral	Neutral
Overall AWM	3.42	Neutral	Neutral

Table 3 presents the data for the academic performance of learners in terms of their average grades during the first and second quarters of the school year 2021 – 2022. Their grades are reflected in Appendix E. It can be gleaned in Table 3 that 2 learners performed "Outstanding". On the other hand, 18 learners fall under "Very Satisfactory" and 12 learners get a "Satisfactory" descriptive equivalent. While 4 learners in "fairly satisfactory". No one in "Excellent," and nobody "Did not meet Expectations". The results show that from the respondents, most of the learners that play Mobile Legends obtain an average grade ranging from 85-89 interpreted as "Very Satisfactory". It appears that Grade 6 learners perform well academically even if they have been playing Mobile Legends.

Table 3. Academic Performance of Grade 6 Mobile Legends Players
 N=36

General Average	Frequency	Descriptive Equivalent
96-100	0	Excellent
90-95	2	Outstanding
85-89	18	Very Satisfactory
80-84	12	Satisfactory
75-79	4	Fairly Satisfactory
74 and below	0	Did Not Meet Expectations
Total	36	

As reflected in Table 4, the statistical test shows that the sex and academic performance of the learners have a p-value of 0.661. The table also indicated the p-value of the frequency of playing and academic performance resulted in 0.241. Both are more than 0.05, which implies that these variables have no significant relationship with the academic performance of Grade 6 learners. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted.

In terms of the average time spent playing, the table shows a p-value of 0.78 (greater than .05) when correlated with academic performance. This also implies that the learners' academic performance is not affected by the average time spent playing.

Table 4 also reveals that online gaming attitudes and academic performance have no significant relationship having a p-value of 0.32 which led to the acceptance of the null hypothesis. This means that learners were not academically affected even if they had been playing Mobile Legends. These results further imply that the profile variables of the learners do not affect their academic performance.

The above findings of this research give support to the findings of Garnada (2020) that found no significant relationship between online game addiction and learners' attitudes toward study habits. This means that their study habits are unaffected by their online gaming addiction.

Table 4. Correlational Analysis of the Relationship Between the Profile and Academic Performance of Grade 6 Learners

Profile Variables	Academic Performance		
	Statistical Test	Value	Decision
Sex	Chi-Square	1.594	Accept H_0
	P-Value	0.661	
Frequency of Playing	Chi-Square	15.004	Accept H_0
	P-Value	0.241	
Average Time Spent	Chi-Square	8.0688	Accept H_0
	P-Value	0.78	
Online Gaming Attitudes	Chi-Square	12.2964	Accept H_0
	P-Value	0.32	

5 Conclusion and Recommendation

Based on the analyses of the gathered data, the following are the salient findings of the study. There are 23 or 63.89% male Mobile Legend players and 13 or 36.11% female Mobile Legend players. 17 learners play once a week, 5 learners who play twice a week, 7 learners who play three to four times a week, 1 learner who plays five to six times a week, and 6 learners who play every day. A total of 18 learners spend less than an hour playing while 13 learners play for one to two hours. Furthermore, 3 learners play for three to four hours, 1 learner who plays for five to six hours, and 1 learner who spends more than six hours playing the game. There are 4 learners with fairly satisfactory grades, 12 learners with satisfactory grades, 18 learners with very satisfactory grades, and 2 learners with outstanding grades.

The sex distribution and academic performance have a p-value of 0.661. The value is more than 0.05 which means that there is no significant relationship between sex distribution and academic performance. Thus, the null hypothesis is accepted. The frequency of playing and academic performance has a p-value of 0.241, the value is more than 0.05 which means that there is no significant relationship between the frequency of playing and academic performance.

Thus, the null hypothesis is accepted. There is also no significant relationship between the average time spent playing Mobile Legends and academic performance having a p-value of 0.78. Thus, the null hypothesis is accepted. Further, the results showed no significant relationship between online gaming attitudes and academic performance with a p-value of 0.32. Thus, the null hypothesis is accepted.

Based on the findings, the following conclusions are drawn. Grade 6 Mobile Legends players of Mandaluyong Addition Hills Elementary School are males and play seldom a week. The Grade 6 learners spend a short time playing Mobile Legends

in a day. The Grade 6 learners manifest positive attitudes while playing the Mobile Legends. The academic performance of Grade 6 Mobile Legends players is very satisfactory. Playing Mobile Legends does not affect the academic performance of Grade 6 learners.

Based on the salient findings and conclusions, the following recommendations are offered: Parents or home learning partners should sustain providing guidance and motivate the learners to limit their gaming exposure and help them excel in their studies. Learners should be encouraged to improve further their academic performance from very satisfactory to an outstanding or excellent level. The researcher recommends identifying more factors, that are rooted in playing Mobile Legends, that can affect their academic performance. Similar studies should be conducted to determine how other online games affect the learners' study habits and performance in school.

References

- Aviso, Andre & Bachelor, & Maderazo, Merriene & Katleene, A & Castro, & Carl, Joshua & Quiroga, Catherine & Jane, & Espineda, Justine & Vincent, V. (2021). "Impact on the Behavior of Students Due to Online Technology Gaming and Its Effect on their Academic Performance."
- Dumrique, D. O., & Castillo, J. G. (2018). Online Gaming: Impact On The Academic Performance and Social Behavior Of The Students In Polytechnic University Of The Philippines Laboratory High School. *KnE Social Sciences*, 3(6), 1205–1210.
- Garnada, V. (2020). "Online Gaming Addiction and Academic Attitudes: The Case of College Students in The Philippines. *International Review of Humanities and Scientific Research*"
- Griffiths, M. D., & Meredith, A. (2009). Videogame Addiction and its Treatment. *Journal of Contemporary Psychotherapy*, 39(4), 247–253.
- Kircaburun, K., & Griffiths, M. D. (2018). Instagram addiction and the Big Five of personality: The mediating role of self-liking. *Journal of Behavioral Addictions*, 7(1), 158–170.
- Kishimoto, R. T., Prasetyo, Y. T., Persada, S. F., & Redi, A. A. N. P. (2021). Filipino Generation Z on Mobile Legends during COVID-19: A Determination of Playtime and Satisfaction. *International Journal of Information and Education Technology*, 11(8), 381–386.
- Kuss, D. J., & Lopez-Fernandez, O. (2016). Internet addiction and problematic Internet use: A systematic review of clinical research. *World Journal of Psychiatry*, 6(1), 143–176.
- Verecio, R. L. (2017). Online Gaming Addiction among BSIT Students of Leyte Normal University Philippines and its Implications towards Academic Performance. *Indian Journal of Science and Technology*, 11(47), 1–4.